

Final Destination 5 (2011)



Insidious (2011)



Paranormal Activity 3 (2011)



Scream 4 (2011)



Don't Be Afraid of the Dark (2011)



Dream House (2011)





Fright Night (2011)



Shark Night 3D (2011)



The Thing (2011)



Abraham Lincoln: Vampire Hunter (2012)



Chernobyl Diaries (2012)



Dark Shadows (2012)



House at the End of the Street (2012)



Paranormal Activity 4 (2012)



Silent Hill: Revelation 3D (2012)



Sinister (2012)



The Cabin in the Woods (2012)



The Devil Inside (2012)



The Possession (2012)



The Raven (2012)





Carrie (2013)



Evil Dead (2013)



Insidious Chapter 2 (2013)



Mama (2013)



Texas Chainsaw 3D (2013)



The Conjuring (2013)



The Last Exorcism Part II (2013)



You're Next (2013)



Annabelle (2014)



Deliver Us from Evil (2014)



Ouija (2014)



Paranormal Activity: The Marked Ones (2014)



A Haunted House 2 (2014)



Devil's Due (2014)







Krampus (2015)



Poltergeist (2015)





The Gallows (2015)



The Lazarus Effect (2015)



The Woman in Black 2: Angel of Death (2015)



Paranormal Activity: The Ghost Dimension (2015)

